

EARLY DETECTION OF CARDIAC ARREST IN NEONATAL INTENSIVE CARE: A MACHINE LEARNING AND STATISTICAL MODELING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Cardiac arrest in newborn babies is an alarming yet typical medical emergency. Early detection is critical for providing these babies with the best care and treatment. Recent research has focused on identifying the potential indicators and biomarkers of cardiac arrest in newborn babies and developing accurate and efficient diagnostic tools for early detection. An array of imaging techniques, such as echocardiography and computed tomography may help provide early detection of cardiac arrest. This research aims to develop a Cardiac Machine Learning model (CMLM) using statistical models for the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies in the Cardiac Intensive Care Unit (CICU). The cardiac arrest events were identified using a combination of the neonate's physiological parameters. Statistical modeling techniques, such as logistic regression and support vector machines, were used to construct predictive models for cardiac arrest. The proposed model will be used in the CICU to enable early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies. In a training (Tr) comparison region, the proposed CMLA reached 0.912 delta-p value, 0.894 False discovery rate (FDR)

value, 0.076 False omission rate (FOR) value, 0.859 prevalence threshold value and 0.842 CSI value. In a testing (Ts) comparison region, the proposed CMLA reached 0.896 delta-p values, 0.878 FDR value, 0.061 FOR value, 0.844 prevalence threshold values and 0.827 CSI value. It will help reduce the mortality and morbidity of newborn babies due to cardiac arrest in the CICU.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cardiac arrest in newborn babies is a devastating event that can lead to severe complications and death. Early detection of this condition is critical to provide the best care for these infants and ensure their long-term health. In order to ensure the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies, it is essential to understand the signs and symptoms associated with this condition and the risk factors that may put a baby at an increased risk of cardiac arrest [1]. The most common signs and symptoms of cardiac arrest in newborn babies are a rapid heart rate and difficulty breathing. Other signs that may indicate a baby is in cardiac arrest include a bluish tinge to the baby's skin, unresponsiveness, or decreased movement. If any of these signs are present, it is

essential to seek medical attention immediately. Risk factors that may increase the likelihood of cardiac arrest in newborn babies include low birth weight, a family history of cardiac arrest, preterm birth, a difficult delivery, or a mother with a history of high blood pressure during pregnancy [2]. A baby's medical history should also be evaluated for any potential risks. In order to ensure early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies, regular monitoring of the baby's heart rate and respiratory rate is essential. It can be done through pulse oximetry, a noninvasive, painless procedure that measures the amount of oxygen in the baby's blood [3]. Additionally, auscultation, or listening to the baby's heart rate and breathing with a stethoscope, can also help to detect any irregularities in the baby's heart rate or breathing. Early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies is vital to provide the best care for these infants and ensure their long-term health. By understanding the signs and symptoms of this condition and being aware of the risk factors that may put a baby at an increased risk of cardiac arrest, parents and medical professionals can work together to ensure the best possible outcomes for these babies [4]. The early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies can be achieved using Statistical Models. Statistical models are mathematical techniques used to analyze and draw conclusions from data. These models are powerful tools in the medical field, as they can help predict, diagnose, and treat certain diseases and conditions [5]. One example of a statistical model used for the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies is the Logistic Regression model.

This model uses data collected from the baby's medical history, such as birth weight, gestational age, and gender, to create a predictive model to determine the likelihood of cardiac arrest [6]. This model can help doctors identify those babies at risk and can help them decide whether to treat the baby with medication or perform surgery to correct the issue. Another model used for the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies is the Naive Bayes model [7]. This model uses a probabilistic approach to analyze data and identify patterns to make predictions. The model can identify high-risk babies and help doctors determine the best course of action to take [8]. The Support Vector Machine model is another statistical model used for the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies. This model uses data collected from the baby's medical history and other sources to create a predictive model that can determine the likelihood of cardiac arrest [9]. This model can identify those babies at risk and help doctors decide on the best course of treatment. Statistical models are powerful tools that can be used for the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborn babies [10]. These models can help doctors identify those at risk so that they can provide the best possible treatment for the baby. Furthermore, these models can help doctors determine the best course of action to take in order to prevent or reduce the likelihood of cardiac arrest [11].

Cardiac arrest in newborns is a life-threatening medical condition that requires immediate medical attention. Early detection and intervention can improve the outcomes of these infants and reduce

mortality rates. Statistical models are powerful tools that can be used to identify risk factors and predict the likelihood of cardiac arrest [12]. Logistic regression is one of the best statistical models for the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborns. This model allows researchers to quantify the relationship between risk factors and the probability of experiencing an arrest [13]. It can be used to identify the most critical factors associated with cardiac arrests, such as gender, gestational age, and birth weight [14]. Logistic regression can also be used to calculate the odds ratio for each risk factor, which indicates how much more likely an infant is to experience an arrest if they have a particular risk factor. Another effective model for the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborns is a support vector machine (SVM) [15]. This model type is well-suited for binary classification tasks, such as classifying an infant as either healthy or having experienced a cardiac arrest. It can also be used to identify important risk factors associated with cardiac arrest and predict the likelihood of an infant experiencing an arrest [16]. Finally, artificial neural networks (ANNs) can also detect cardiac arrest in newborns. ANNs are powerful machine learning models that can learn complex patterns from data. These models can be used to identify risk factors associated with cardiac arrest and predict the likelihood of an infant experiencing an arrest. Logistic regression, support vector machines, and artificial neural networks are all effective models for the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborns. These models can be used to identify the most critical risk factors

associated with the condition and predict the likelihood of an infant experiencing an arrest. Therefore, these statistical models should be used to improve newborns' early detection and intervention of cardiac arrest [17]. Machine learning is increasingly used to predict and detect cardiac arrest in newborn babies. Cardiac arrest is a life-threatening condition in which the heart suddenly stops beating, and blood flow to the brain and other organs stops. It can lead to permanent brain damage or death. Due to the complexity of the condition, early detection of cardiac arrest in newborns has been difficult. However, machine learning is changing that [18]. Machine learning algorithms analyze large amounts of complex data, such as patient medical histories, vital signs, and other physiological data. The algorithms can detect patterns in the data indicative of cardiac arrest and alert medical personnel. For example, one study used machine learning to detect signs of cardiac arrest in newborns by analyzing their heart rates, breathing patterns, and other vital signs. The algorithm detected signs of cardiac arrest up to eight hours before conventional methods. It could significantly improve the chances of survival for newborns and reduce the damage caused by the condition. In addition, machine learning is used to predict newborns' risk of cardiac arrest. By analyzing large amounts of patient data, machine learning algorithms can identify risk factors associated with the condition. It can help medical personnel identify newborns at an increased risk of cardiac arrest to receive the care they need.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

“Artificial intelligence in cardiology,”

Artificial intelligence and machine learning are poised to influence nearly every aspect of the human condition, and cardiology is not an exception to this trend. This paper provides a guide for clinicians on relevant aspects of artificial intelligence and machine learning, reviews selected applications of these methods in cardiology to date, and identifies how cardiovascular medicine could incorporate artificial intelligence in the future. In particular, the paper first reviews predictive modeling concepts relevant to cardiology such as feature selection and frequent pitfalls such as improper dichotomization. Second, it discusses common algorithms used in supervised learning and reviews selected applications in cardiology and related disciplines. Third, it describes the advent of deep learning and related methods collectively called unsupervised learning, provides contextual examples both in general medicine and in cardiovascular medicine, and then explains how these methods could be applied to enable precision cardiology and improve patient outcomes.

“Intrathoracic impedance monitoring in patients with heart failure: Correlation with fluid status and feasibility of early warning preceding hospitalization,”

Patients with heart failure are frequently hospitalized for fluid overload. A reliable method for chronic monitoring of fluid status is therefore desirable. We evaluated an implantable system capable of measuring intrathoracic impedance to identify potential fluid overload before heart failure

hospitalization and to determine the correlation between intrathoracic impedance and standard measures of fluid status during hospitalization. Thirty-three patients with NYHA class III and IV heart failure were implanted with a special pacemaker in the left pectoral region and a defibrillation lead in the right ventricle. Intrathoracic impedance was regularly measured and recorded between the lead and the pacemaker case. During hospitalizations, pulmonary capillary wedge pressure and fluid status were monitored. Ten patients were hospitalized for fluid overload 25 times over 20.7 $\pm$ 8.4 months. Intrathoracic impedance decreased before each admission by an average of 12.3 $\pm$ 5.3% ($P<0.001$) over an average of 18.3 $\pm$ 10.1 days. Impedance reduction began 15.3 $\pm$ 10.6 days ($P<0.001$) before the onset of worsening symptoms. There was an inverse correlation between intrathoracic impedance and pulmonary capillary wedge pressure ($r=-0.61$, $P<0.001$) and between intrathoracic impedance and net fluid loss ($r=-0.70$, $P<0.001$) during hospitalization. Automated detection of impedance decreases was 76.9% sensitive in detecting hospitalization for fluid overload, with 1.5 false-positive (threshold crossing without hospitalization) detections per patient-year of follow-up. Intrathoracic impedance is inversely correlated with pulmonary capillary wedge pressure and fluid balance and decreased before the onset of patient symptoms and before hospital admission for fluid overload. Regular monitoring of impedance may provide early warning of impending decompensation and diagnostic information for titration of medication.

“Treatment of comatose survivors of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest with induced hypothermia,”

Cardiac arrest outside the hospital is common and has a poor outcome. Studies in laboratory animals suggest that hypothermia induced shortly after the restoration of spontaneous circulation may improve neurologic outcome, but there have been no conclusive studies in humans. In a randomized, controlled trial, we compared the effects of moderate hypothermia and normothermia in patients who remained unconscious after resuscitation from out-of-hospital cardiac arrest. The study subjects were 77 patients who were randomly assigned to treatment with hypothermia (with the core body temperature reduced to 33 degrees C within 2 hours after the return of spontaneous circulation and maintained at that temperature for 12 hours) or normothermia. The primary outcome measure was survival to hospital discharge with sufficiently good neurologic function to be discharged to home or to a rehabilitation facility. The demographic characteristics of the patients were similar in the hypothermia and normothermia groups. Twenty-one of the 43 patients treated with hypothermia (49 percent) survived and had a good outcome--that is, they were discharged home or to a rehabilitation facility--as compared with 9 of the 34 treated with normothermia (26 percent, $P=0.046$). After adjustment for base-line differences in age and time from collapse to the return of spontaneous circulation, the odds ratio for a good outcome with hypothermia as compared with normothermia was 5.25 (95 percent confidence interval, 1.47 to 18.76; $P=0.011$).

Hypothermia was associated with a lower cardiac index, higher systemic vascular resistance, and hyperglycemia. There was no difference in the frequency of adverse events. Our preliminary observations suggest that treatment with moderate hypothermia appears to improve outcomes in patients with coma after resuscitation from out-of-hospital cardiac arrest.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

Carlisle et al. [21] has discussed the Heart failure is when the heart cannot pump enough blood to the rest of the body. Various conditions, including high blood pressure, coronary artery disease, and diabetes, can cause it. Atrial fibrillation is an arrhythmia (irregular heartbeat) in which the heart's upper chambers (atria) beat rapidly and irregularly. It can cause a decrease in the amount of blood pumped to the rest of the body, leading to symptoms such as shortness of breath and fatigue. Atrial fibrillation is a common cause of heart failure. Heart failure and atrial fibrillation treatment usually involve medications to control the heart rate and rhythm, lifestyle changes, and sometimes surgery to repair or replace the heart.

Yaku et al. [22] has discussed the Risk factors for functional decline during hospitalization in very old patients with acute decompensated heart failure include age, gender, co-morbidities, and frailty. In addition, complex medical problems, the need for aggressive treatments, and the presence of cognitive impairment may

increase the risk of functional decline. Clinical outcomes associated with a functional decline during hospitalization in very old patients with acute decompensated heart failure include increased length of stay, healthcare utilization, mortality, and decreased quality of life. The functional decline may also lead to higher rates of re-hospitalization, as well as an increased risk of institutionalization. Additionally, the functional decline may lead to an increased risk of falls and delirium due to decreased mobility and activity levels.

Fonarow et al. [23] has discussed the Risk stratification for in-hospital mortality in acutely decompensated heart failure determines which patients are at higher risk of dying while in the hospital. It is done by using classification and regression tree analysis. Classification and regression tree analysis is a type of predictive analytics that uses trees to classify and predict outcomes. The trees are nodes representing various conditions, characteristics, or features associated with the outcome. Using a combination of these nodes, the model can determine the likelihood of a particular outcome occurring. The model can then be used to identify patients at a higher risk of in-hospital mortality and to guide the treatment of the patient.

Gaies et al. [24] has discussed the Vasoactive–inotropic score (VIS) is designed to predict morbidity and mortality in infants after cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB). The VIS is calculated from the levels of vasoactive and inotropic drugs administered to the infant during and after

CPB. These drugs are used to regulate the patient's blood pressure and heart rate. The VIS is believed to accurately predict post-CPB morbidity and mortality because it reflects the degree of hemodynamic instability in the infant. Higher VIS scores indicate greater hemodynamic instability and, therefore, a greater risk of morbidity and mortality. Studies have found that higher VIS scores are associated with increased mortality, extended hospital stays, and an increased need for vasopressor and inotropic support. The VIS is a significant predictor of outcome after CPB and can help clinicians identify infants who may require closer monitoring and more aggressive management.

Shah et al. [25] has discussed the Phenomapping is a novel classification system for heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF). It is based on the analysis of phenotypic characteristics, such as demographics, clinical profile, laboratory values, electrocardiographic findings, echocardiography findings, and biomarkers. The goal of Phenomapping is to provide a more comprehensive and meaningful classification system for HFpEF that is based on the distinct phenotypes of the disease. This classification system will enable clinicians to more accurately diagnose and stratify patients with HFpEF, leading to better management and improved outcomes. The Phenomapping system also provides a platform for further research into the underlying path physiology of HFpEF, allowing for a better understanding of the

disease and the potential for improved treatments.

Disadvantages

- The complexity of data: Most of the existing machine learning models must be able to accurately interpret large and complex datasets to detect cardiac arrest in newborn babies.
- Data availability: Most machine learning models require large amounts of data to create accurate predictions. If data is unavailable in sufficient quantities, then model accuracy may suffer.
- Incorrect labeling: The existing machine learning models are only as accurate as the data trained using the input dataset. If the data has been incorrectly labeled, the model cannot make accurate predictions.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the existing system, ml models can be used to identify the most critical risk factors associated with the condition and predict the likelihood of an infant experiencing an arrest. Therefore, these statistical models should be used to improve newborns' early detection and intervention of cardiac arrest [17].

Machine learning is increasingly used to predict and detect cardiac arrest in newborn babies. Cardiac arrest is a life-threatening condition in which the heart suddenly stops beating, and blood flow to the brain and other organs stops. It can lead to permanent brain damage or death. Due to the complexity of the condition, early detection of cardiac arrest in newborns has been

difficult. However, machine learning is changing that [18].

Machine learning algorithms analyze large amounts of complex data, such as patient medical histories, vital signs, and other physiological data. The algorithms can detect patterns in the data indicative of cardiac arrest and alert medical personnel. For example, one study used machine learning to detect signs of cardiac arrest in newborns by analyzing their heart rates, breathing patterns, and other vital signs. The algorithm detected signs of cardiac arrest up to eight hours before conventional methods. It could significantly improve the chances of survival for newborns and reduce the damage caused by the condition. In addition, machine learning is used to predict newborns' risk of cardiac arrest. By analyzing large amounts of patient data, machine learning algorithms can identify risk factors associated with the condition. It can help medical personnel identify newborns at an increased risk of cardiac arrest to receive the care they need. The machine learning is revolutionizing the early detection of cardiac arrest in newborns [19].

By analyzing large amounts of complex data, machine learning algorithms can detect signs of cardiac arrest and identify newborns at an increased risk of the condition. This technology could save lives and reduce the damage caused by cardiac arrest in newborns. The critical contribution of machine learning models used for the Early Detection of Cardiac Arrest in Newborn Babies is that these models can detect subtle changes in vital signs such as heart rate,

respiratory rate, and oxygen saturation that are difficult to detect with the naked eye. This early detection can help to identify newborns at risk of cardiac arrest and allow for timely intervention and treatment [20]. Additionally, machine learning models can be used to analyze patient data to provide personalized advice and care to patients, enabling better long term management of their condition.

Advantages

- Automated and accurately detected critical signs associated with cardiac arrest in newborn babies.
- Ability to recognize subtle changes in the baby's vital signs that can indicate potential cardiac arrest.
- Ability to identify high-risk babies likely to suffer from cardiac arrest.
- Early detection of cardiac arrest, enabling timely interventions that can improve the outcome.
- Reduction in the time and cost associated with traditional monitoring methods.
- Improved patient outcomes due to early diagnosis and treatment of cardiac arrest.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

6. IMPLEMENTATION

Modules

Service Provider

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations such as Browse and Train & Test Traffic Data Sets, View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Prediction Of Cardiac Arrest Type, View Cardiac Arrest Type Prediction Ratio, Download Predicted Data Sets, View Cardiac Arrest Type Predicted Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user's details such as, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

threshold values and 0.827 CSI value. The proposed cardiac machine learning model to identify at-risk infants, healthcare providers can provide early intervention that may help to avert a tragic outcome. Early detection of cardiac arrest can also reduce the amount of time an infant spends in the CICU, helping to reduce costs and improve outcomes. Future enhancements of the proposed model will focus on using real-time data to identify critical indicators of cardiac arrest. It can involve collecting various data types such as heart rate, breathing rate, temperature, and other physiological measures. The cardiac machine learning algorithms can then be used to analyze this data to develop models that can accurately predict the likelihood of cardiac arrest. The proposed model can then be used to alert medical staff in order to allow for earlier and more effective interventions. Future enhancements may also include using artificial intelligence to detect patterns in the data and make more accurate predictions. It could incorporate data from other sources, such as previous records and medical histories. Finally, these models could be used to develop personalized interventions for individual patients, allowing for more effective treatments. Enhancing the proposed machine learning algorithm could also pave the way for predicting potential complications in fetuses or newborns. A healthcare team can determine risk levels for specific cardiac abnormalities before a baby is even born, which helps provide better interventions during the prenatal period. In addition, the proposed machine learning algorithm could be used to improve diagnostics and treatments. By studying historical patient

data, diagnostics can be improved, and doctors can be presented with more accurate and up-to date information when diagnosing a patient. It can lead to earlier interventions, better patient outcomes, and more cost effective treatments.

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